

Educational characteristics	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9
Understandability	X		X						
Content Quality	X	X			X		X	X	X
Accuracy of content	X	X			X	X	X		X
Motivation					X		X		
Cultural aspects	X		X			X	X		X
Navigability	X		X		X	X			X
Appropriate assessments	X				X				
Presentation design	X	X	X		X				X
Appropriate support	X	X	X	X			X		X
Instructional strategies	X								X
Appropriate License	X	X	X						
Interactivity	X		X		X				X
Content discovery		X					X		
Feedback	X	X	X		X	X			
Metadata accuracy			X				X		
Decontextualisation			X						X
Learning goal alignment	X	X			X	X	X		X
Standards compliance		X	X		X				X
Readability	X								
appropriateness of terminology and notations	X								
Select easily the most suitable learning unit	X								
combined	X								
Reasonableness	X								
Self-containedness	X								
Relevance	X								
Multimedia inserts	X								
course	X								
resources	X								
Learning outcomes	X								
activities	X								
Appropriate assessments and self-assessments	X								
Reflective and deeper learning	X								
Extensibility	X								
Distribution		X							
Academic program orientation		X							
Adopt instructional philosophies		X							
Consider the intellectual property rights		X							

